

Market performance of publicly sponsored versus privately sponsored banking: Evidence from an emerging market

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Abstract

Historical, Taiwan has a mixture of the publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking, but there has been little investigation of their market performances in the literature. This study seeks to fill the gap. We study the market performance of these two types of banking from three dimensions: liquidity, payoff to investors and price efficiency. Liquidity and price efficiency are related to asset pricing and price discovery. Investor payoff suggests which investors should trade certain stocks and raises questions as to market fairness. All three dimensions have important implications in finance. Our outcomes show there are pros and cons in these three dimensions for public-sponsored- and private-sponsored banking. Future directions for development should include both types and they should learn to embrace their advantages and avoid each other's shortcomings.

Keywords: Publicly sponsored banking, privately sponsored banking, liquidity, payoff to investors, price efficiency.

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1. Introduction

Banking is to the economy as blood is to the human body. That is to say, the banking system serves a very important role in the operation of the economy and the process of development. Many companies financed by the banking system have grown into reputable international corporations large enough to impact the world economy.

The financing system can be categorized into direct and indirect financing. Direct financing refers to transactions conducted through financial markets, while indirect financing involves financial intermediaries or the banking system. In Taiwan, indirect financing takes up about 76% of the financing system¹. This ratio is quite high, in comparison to other developed economies. The phenomena may be related to Taiwan's industrial structure, which is comprised mostly of small or medium scale enterprises. Their lack of plentiful business revenues or property ownership prevents them from accessing capital through the financial market. This has forced them to depend on the banking system to obtain operating capital. These conditions highlight the importance of the role of banking in the process of Taiwan's economic development.

Owing to historical development, Taiwan's banking system can be divided into publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking. Prior to 1990, the indirect financing sector was almost monopolized by publicly sponsored banking. However, in 1990, the Taiwan government opened up the banking sector, allowing the establishment of new privately sponsored banks. Additionally, the government promoted a policy of financial liberalization. These measures stimulated rapid expansion of the private banking sector,

to eventually lead development of the banking system. Even after 35 years (1990-2025), we are still uncertain about the market performance of publicly sponsored vs privately

¹ Data source: Department of Economic Research, Central Bank of Taiwan, 2024.

sponsored banking. There has been little investigation in the literature related to this issue, although it has important implications for government and society. Moreover, Taiwan's experience with the competition between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking would be a valuable reference for other developing countries. These are the motivations for our research.

The objective of this study is to examine and compare the market performance of publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking. In this study, market performance is assumed to include three dimensions: liquidity, payoff to investors, and price efficiency, and all are very important financial objectives. Liquidity is related to asset pricing (O'Hara, 2003). According to the research findings of Amihud and Mendelson (1987, 1991), Brennan and Subrahmanyam (1996) and Amihud et al. (1997), stock price increases with liquidity, and the required rate of return should be higher for illiquid stock. Marvin and Peterson (2007) and Lam and Tam (2011) found that liquidity is an important factor in determining a portfolio's return rate. Payoff to investors relates to what kind of investors (uninformed traders vs informed traders) should trade which type of stock, which concerns market fairness. The topic of liquidity inherently related to the concept of price efficiency. Both liquidity and price efficiency play critical roles in facilitating effective price discovery. Price efficiency refers to how quickly and accurately stock prices respond to new information. If the response is fast and exact, we consider the price efficiency is good; otherwise, it is bad.

We compare the liquidity between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking using the quoted spread (QS) and effective bid-ask spreads (ES). The effective spread is further split into realized spread (RS) and information asymmetry (IA). The former is the payoff to uninformed traders, while the latter is the payoff to informed traders (Huang and Stoll, 1996). Comparing payoffs among different types of traders in publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking stocks helps identify which traders are suited for which stock types. Alternatively, it is possible to determine which option is more equitable when trading publicly sponsored or privately sponsored banking stocks. In our discussion of price efficiency, we use the measures of price error and firm-specific noise specified in Amihud et al. (1997).

The empirical results are summarized below. For liquidity, both QS and ES are significantly lower for privately sponsored banking than for publicly sponsored banking. These spreads are also a measure of the trading cost. Our results suggest that privately sponsored banking has better liquidity and lower trading cost than publicly sponsored banking. In terms of payoff to investors, although the realized spreads are lower for privately sponsored banking

than for publicly sponsored banking, but in terms of information asymmetry, we find the opposite condition. The results imply that it is advantageous for uninformed traders to trade publicly sponsored banking stock, while it is better for informed traders to handle privately sponsored banking stock. Price efficiency is better for publicly sponsored banking than for privately sponsored banking. We assume that this outcome may be related to the better transparency of the publicly sponsored banking.

The rest of the study is arranged as follows. Section 2 contains the literature review and hypothesis development. Section 3 discusses the banking on the Taiwan Stock Exchange (TSEC) and the data sources. Section 4 describes the methodology and variable measures. Section 5 summarizes the empirical results and their implications. Some conclusions are offered in Section 6.

2. Literature review and hypotheses

In this study, we compare liquidity, payoff to investors, and price efficiency between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking. Liquidity remains an important issue in finance. O'Hara (2003) pointed out that liquidity is closely associated with asset pricing. Amihud and Mendelson (1987, 1991) and Amihud et al. (1997) found, other things being equal, the asset price increases with liquidity. In their examination of the relationship between asset price and liquidity, Brennan and Subrahmanyam (1996) concluded that the required rate of return should be higher for illiquid stock. Marvin and Perterson (2007) and Lam and Tam (2011) investigated the connection between portfolio liquidity and return. They found that liquidity is an important factor in deciding the return rate. Huang and Stoll (1996) argued that the realized spread is the payoff to uninformed investors, and that information asymmetry is the payoff to informed traders. Bacidores and Sofianos (2002) and Bessembinder and Venkataraman (2010) further explained and expanded Huang and Stoll's (1996) argument, eventually reaching the same conclusion about payoff to investors. In terms of the price efficiency, Barkhan and Geltner (1995) proved that both information efficiency and price discovery affect stock price. Dow and Gorton (1997) pointed out that the changes to stock prices, which are induced by information efficiency, are related to the feasibility of company projects or financing strategies. Accordingly, it is helpful for capital allocation. Geng et al. (2025) found, whether in long or short run, improved information efficiency may encourage company's product development.

Based on research objectives and the existing literature, we arrive at the following three hypotheses:

H1: There is no difference in liquidity between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking.

H2: There is no difference in investor payoff between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking.

H3: There is no difference in price efficiency between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking.

3. Banking description and data source

In the last 10 years (2015-2024), indirect financing over total financial market has become more important, dominating about 80%-90%² of the financial market. In Taiwan, indirect financing includes banking system, credit unions, and the credit departments of the farmer's and Fisherman's Associations. On both institutional scale and market occupation, the banking system is the largest among these three types of financial institutions.

Deposits in the banking system for the last five years have reached 49219, 52757, 56330, 59427 and 62727 billion NT dollars, with an annual growth rate of about 5.0%-9.17%. The amount of loans is 37826, 40999, 43616, 46485 and 50316 billion NT dollars, respectively, for an annual growth rate of 5.93%-8.39%.³ These statistics confirm the stable growth and vitality of Taiwan's banking system.

Historically, Taiwan has developed both publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking. Prior to the introduction of new banking regulations in 1990, publicly sponsored banking almost completely monopolized the indirect financial market. However, over the next 35 years (from 1990 to 2025), privately sponsored banking worked diligently to acquire experience, putting them on an equal footing with publicly sponsored banking. For example, among the 15 largest banking in Taiwan⁴, six are publicly sponsored and nine are privately sponsored banking. Approximately 20 years ago, the government of Taiwan authorized banks to establish financial holding company, leading some institutions to undergo this transition. Nevertheless, the core operations of these financial holding company remain bank-based.

² Financial Statistics Monthly, Republic of China (Taiwan), 2024.

³ Same a footnote 2.

⁴ See the webpage for the Banking Bureau for Taiwan.

The research data used in this study obtained from the Taiwan Economic Journal (TEJ) include both intra-day and daily data. All banking and financial holding companies included in the sample are listed in Taiwan Stock TSEC, and are classified as either publicly sponsored or privately sponsored banking. Insurance companies, bill financial companies, and security companies are excluded. The sample period is from 1 July 2023 to 30 June 2025. This sample period was selected because of the ending of the covid-19 pandemic in January 2023. There was no major event disrupting the stock market which may bias the empirical results in this sample period so the sample was deemed representative.

4. Research methods

The measures of liquidity, payoff to investors and price efficiency are discussed in this section. Robust testing was also carried out to examine the study's empirical results.

1). Liquidity⁵

The quoted spread and effective spread are used to measure liquidity. The quoted spread is the difference between the lowest ask price and the highest bid price for a transaction. It is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Quoted spread: } QS_{it} = ((ask_{it} - bid_{it}) / mid_{it}) / 2, \quad (1)$$

Where ask_{it} is the lowest ask price for stock i at time t ; bid_{it} is the highest bid price; mid_{it} is the simple average of the bid-ask price. The bid-ask spread is measured as a round-trip cost, ordinarily, for just a single trade. Then, the bid-ask spread is divided by 2.

The problem with the quoted spread is that the actual trading does not take place at the bid or ask price, meaning that it may be a biased estimator of trading cost. Thus, the effective spread is employed, which is computed as follows:

$$\text{Effective spread: } ES_{it} = q_{it} \cdot (p_{it} - mid_{it}) / mid_{it}, \quad (2)$$

where q_{it} is an indicator variable with a value of +1 under a buy-initiated trade ($p_{it} > mid_{it}$); it has a value of -1 under a sell-initiated trade ($p_{it} < mid_{it}$); and its value is 0 if p_{it} is equal

⁵ For more details, please refer to other paper: "Widening price limit effects: evidence from an emerging stock market", Applied Economics Vol 52(13), 2020.

to mid_{it} . The p_{it} is a transactional price for stock i at time t .

2) Payoff to investors⁶

Huang and Stoll's (1996) methodology was applied to decompose the effective spread into the realized spread and information asymmetry. It is thought that the realized spread and information asymmetry is the payoff to uninformed traders and informed traders in a trade, respectively. The realized spread and information asymmetry are calculated as follows:

$$\text{Realized spread: } RS_{it} = q_{it}(p_{it} - mid_{i,t+5min})/mid_{it}, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Information asymmetry: } IA_{it} = q_{it}(mid_{i,t+5min} - mid_{it})/mid_{it}. \quad (4)$$

where $mid_{i,t+5min}$ is the midpoint price 5 minutes after a trade. Hendershott et al. (2011) assumed that dealers or uninformed traders would close their position at the midpoint price 5 minutes after a trade. Huang and Stoll (1996) argued that a trader would realize his earnings only after a price reversal. Bacidores and Sofianos (2002) and Bessembinder and Venkataraman (2010) stated that the liquidity supplier's revenue net losses to informed traders can be assessed by the realized spread. Moreover, they thought that information asymmetry is the amount paid to informed traders, as measured by equation (4).

3) Price efficiency⁷

Here, two statistics are used to measure price efficiency. The first being the dispersion of individual stock returns around market returns, as developed by Amihud et al. (1997).

From the market model, we get

$$R_{it} - \hat{\alpha}_i - \hat{\beta}_i MR_t = \hat{\varepsilon}_{it},$$

⁶ For more details, please refer to our paper: "The Impact of Post-trade Transparency on Investors: Evidence from an Emerging Market", Journal of Finance Issues 20(2), 2022, 1-9. This is our another paper.

⁷ Please refer to our past work: "The impact of post-trade transparency on price efficiency and price discovery—evidence from the Taiwan Stock Exchange", Managerial Finance Vol 45(8), 2019.

For day t, the relative return dispersion (RRD) is calculated as:

$$RRD_{t1} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\varepsilon}_{it}^2, \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{\varepsilon}_{it}$ is the market model residual of stock i on day t; and n is the number of stocks in the sample. The differences between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking indicate the price efficiency gap.

The second measure is the firm-specific noise in the lag market model (Amihud et al. (1997)), calculated as follows:

$$R_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_i RM_t + \beta_i RM_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (6)$$

where R_{it} is the return for stock i on day t; RM_t and RM_{t-1} are the market returns for day t and t-1, respectively; ε_{it} is the error term.

From $(R_{it} - \hat{\alpha}_i - \hat{\beta}_{i1} MR_t - \hat{\beta}_{i2} MR_{t-1}) = \hat{\varepsilon}_{it}$, and we get

$$RRD_{t2} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\varepsilon}_{it}^2 \quad (7)$$

RRD_{t2} is a proxy for firm-specific noise. In a word, the higher the values of RRD_{t1} and RRD_{t2} , the less the price efficiency.

4) Robust testing

Differences in liquidity and payoff to investors between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking may be caused by other unconsidered factors. To overcome this shortcoming, the multiple regression methodology developed by Madhavan et al. (2005) and Hendershott et al. (2011) is applied for robust testing. The regression model is formulated as follows:

$$S_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 Vol_{i,t} + \beta_2 Vtrn_{i,t} + \beta_3 Dummy_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (8)$$

where S_{it} is the average quoted- or effective spread of stock i on day t; $Vol_{i,t}$ is the daily traded shares (in thousands) of stock i for day t; $Vtrn_{i,t}$ is the volatility of stock i for day t, which is defined as the highest price minus the lowest price for each day; $Dummy_{i,t}$ is a dummy variable, with value of 1 if it is for publicly sponsored banking; otherwise its value is 0; $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ is an error term, assuming it satisfies the classical rules.

5. Empirical results

This section presents the empirical results obtained in this study and discuss their implications.

Descriptive statistics

Table 1 shows descriptive statistics for publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking. Examining the stocks in each portfolio, it can be found: 1) the difference in mean price for each portfolio has a small gap (24.71 vs 25.95); 2) the market value for publicly sponsored banking is larger than the other (265101 vs 179579); 3) the volatility of privately sponsored banking is higher (1.66 vs 0.87); 4) the turnover rate of privately sponsored banking is larger (0.20 vs 0.14). In a word, the privately sponsored banking has heavier trading and larger price volatility.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics

This table shows the mean values of daily closing price (in NTD), daily market value (in million NTD), volatility (variance of daily return, %), and turnover rate for the publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking, respectively. The computed period is from 1 July 2023 to 30 June 2024.

Publicly sponsored banking	Mean	Max.	Min.
Price	24.71	47.42	11.96
Market value	265101	695637	9232
Volatility	0.87	1.41	0.41
Turnover rate	0.14	0.22	0.07
Privately sponsored banking	Mean	Max	Min
Price	25.95	71.88	5.41
Market value	179579	850593	5727
Volatility	1.66	8.96	0.29
Turnover rate	0.20	0.99	0.0

Liquidity

The quoted spread and effective spread are examined at the same time. Usually, investors pay a lower trading cost in a good liquidity market; otherwise, higher trading cost is higher. The results are shown in Table 2 and Table 3. Whether taken as a whole or for a specific time interval, both the quoted spread and effective spread are significantly larger for publicly sponsored banking than for privately sponsored banking. For example, the overall quoted (effective) spread for publicly sponsored banking is 13.23 (13.24), while for privately sponsored banking is 12.62 (12.52). For the time interval from 11:00 to 11:30, its value is 13.41 (13.40) for publicly sponsored banking and 12.79 (12.61) for privately sponsored banking. The difference in the quoted (effective) spread between these two types of banking gradually becomes larger as closing time approaches.

The government of Taiwan has been promoting financial liberalization for the last 40 years. Under this impetus, privately sponsored banking has expanded rapidly and flourished, while publicly sponsored banking are subjected to more political constraints, hampering their development, flexibility and trading frequency. This may be the cause of higher trading costs for publicly sponsored banking.

Table 2 Quoted spread (QS)

The quoted spread is calculated as follows: $QS_{it} = ((Ask_{it} - Bid_{it}) / Mid_{it}) / 2$,

where Bid_{it} and Ask_{it} are the bid and ask price for stock i at time t , respectively; and Mid_{it} is the midpoint of the bid- and ask prices that are concurrent with the quotes. The numbers in columns (1) and (2) indicate the intra-data means. The values in column (3) give the difference between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking. The symbols *, **, and *** indicate significance at 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively, from the t test.

	Publicly sponsored banking (1)	Privately sponsored banking (2)	Diff. (3)
Total	13.23	12.62	0.61***
9:00—9:30	13.44	13.37	0.07*
9:30—10:00	13.32	13.12	0.20**
10:00—10:30	13.37	12.91	0.46***
10:30—11:00	13.41	12.80	0.61***
11:00—11:30	13.41	12.79	0.62***

11:30—12:00	13.29	12.56	0.73 ^{***}
12:00—12:30	13.17	12.28	0.89 ^{***}
12:30—13:00	12.96	12.08	0.88 ^{***}
13:00-13:30	12.76	11.90	0.86 ^{***}

Table 3 Effective spread (ES)

The effective spread is calculated as follows: $ES_{it} = q_{it} (P_{it} - Mid_{it}) / Mid_{it}$,

where P_{it} is the transaction price for stock i at time t ; Mid_{it} is the midpoint between the bid and ask prices that are concurrent with the quotes; q_{it} is an indicator variable, which is +1 if $P_{it} > Mid_{it}$ or -1 if $P_{it} < Mid_{it}$. The numbers in columns (1) and (2) indicate the intra-data means. The values in column (3) indicate the difference between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking. The symbols *, ** and *** indicate significance at 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively, according to the t test.

	Publicly sponsored banking (1)	Privately sponsored banking (2)	Diff. (3)
Total	13.24	12.52	0.72 ^{***}
9:00—9:30	13.42	13.29	0.13 [*]
9:30—10:00	13.31	13.03	0.28 ^{**}
10:00—10:30	13.37	12.82	0.55 ^{***}
10:30—11:00	13.40	12.71	0.69 ^{***}
11:00—11:30	13.40	12.61	0.78 ^{***}
11:30—12:00	13.29	12.43	0.86 ^{***}
12:00—12:30	13.16	12.16	1.00 ^{***}
12:30—13:00	12.95	11.98	0.97 ^{***}
13:00—13:30	12.75	11.81	0.94 ^{***}

In a word, the H1 is rejected and there is a significant difference in liquidity between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking.

Payoff to investors

Following Huang and Stoll's method (1996), the effective spread is decomposed into the realized spread and information asymmetry, as equations (3) and (4), the suggested payoffs to uninformed traders and informed traders, respectively.

(1) Payoff to uninformed traders

The results are presented in Table 4. As can be seen in Table 4, the payoff higher for publicly sponsored banking investors than for their privately sponsored banking counterparts. Overall, the payoff to publicly sponsored banking investors is 12.76, while for privately sponsored banking investors it is 11.94. For the time interval from 9:30 to 10:00, the value is 12.99 for publicly sponsored banking investors and 12.53 for private-sponsored banking investors. Generally, publicly sponsored banking are more strictly monitored, leveling the playing field for uninformed investors, leading to a better payoff for them.

Table 4 Realized spread (RS)

The realized spread is calculated as : $RS_{it} = q_{it} (P_{it} - Mid_{i,t+5min}) / Mid_{it}$,

where P_{it} is the transaction price for stock i at time t ; Mid_{it} is the midpoint between the bid- and ask prices that are concurrent with the quotes; $mid_{i,t+5min}$ is the midpoint price 5 minutes after a trade; q_{it} is an indicator variable, which is +1 if $P_{it} > Mid_{it}$ or -1 if $P_{it} < Mid_{it}$. The numbers in columns (1) and (2) represent the means of the intra-data. The values in column (3) indicate the difference between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking. The symbols *, ** and *** indicate significance at 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively, from the t test.

	Publicly sponsored banking (1)	Privately sponsored banking (2)	Diff. (3)
Total	12.76	11.94	0.82***
9:00—9:30	12.78	12.62	0.16*
9:30—10:00	12.99	12.53	0.46***
10:00—10:30	12.03	12.32	-0.29*
10:30-11:00	13.03	12.15	0.88***
11:00—11:30	13.01	12.04	0.97***

11:30—12:00	12.86	11.89	0.97***
12:00—12:30	12.59	11.59	1.00***
12:30—13:00	12.36	11.33	1.03***
13:00—13:30	12.19	11.15	1.04***

(2) Payoff to informed traders

First, Table 5 shows the observed trend of information asymmetry across time intervals. Information asymmetry is highest in the time interval from 9:00 to 9:30, due to the information accumulation from last day’s closing. As trading continues, asymmetry gradually decreases. But it may rise after 10:30, with the entry of new information into the market. The trend becomes more obvious as closing time approaches.

Secondly, Table 5 shows higher information asymmetry for privately sponsored banking than for publicly sponsored banking. Overall, the values are 0.58 for privately sponsored banking and 0.46 for publicly sponsored banking. For the time interval from 9:30 to 10:00, the value is 0.49 for privately sponsored banking and 0.32 for public-sponsored banking. These results and our supposition align with the conclusion of Bessembinder and Maxwell (2008) and Schultz and Song (2019). They argued that greater

transparency makes it more difficult for informed traders to gain the upper hand over uninformed traders, and it creates fairer trading conditions.

In short, the H2 is rejected. The trading of privately sponsored banking stock favors informed traders, while it is more advantageous for uninformed traders to focus on publicly sponsored banking when trading.

Table 5 Information asymmetry (IA)

The information asymmetry is calculated as follows: $IA_{it} = q_{it} (Mid_{i,t+5min} - Mid_{it}) / Mid_{it}$, where Mid_{it} is the midpoint between the bid- and ask prices that are concurrent with the quotes; $mid_{i,t+5min}$ is the midpoint price 5 minutes after a trade; q_{it} is an indicator variable, which is +1 if $P_{it} > Mid_{it}$ or -1 if $P_{it} < Mid_{it}$. The numbers in column (1) and (2) indicate the means of the intra-data. The values in column (3) give the difference between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking. The symbols *, ** and *** indicate significance at 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively, from the t test.

	Public sponsored banking (1)	Privately sponsored banking (2)	Diff. (3)
Total	0.46	0.58	-0.12***
1 9:00—9:30	0.65	0.67	-0.02
2 9:30—10:00	0.32	0.49	-0.17***
3 10:00—10:30	0.33	0.49	-0.16**
4 10:30—11:00	0.37	0.56	-0.19***
5 11:00-11:30	0.39	0.59	-0.20***
6 11:30-12:00	0.43	0.55	-0.12***
7 12:00—12:30	0.57	0.57	0.00
8 12:30—13:00	0.59	0.64	-0.05**
9 13:00—13:30	0.56	0.66	-0.10**

Robust testing

Differences in liquidity and investor payoffs between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking may be due to other unconsidered factors. The literature shows that liquidity and payoffs to investors may be influenced by trading shares and price volatility, so these factors should be excluded when measuring the difference.

The methodology of Madhavan et al. (2005) and Hendershott et al. (2011), as formulated in equation (8), is used for robust multivariate regression testing.

The results are shown in Table 6, only focusing on the coefficients of the dummy variables. For example, the dummy coefficient of the quoted spread is 0.43, which is significant at 1% significance level. After controlling for other related variables, the results summarized in Table 6, confirm the robustness of our earlier results in Tables 2 to 5.

Table 6 Robust testing

The model is formulated as follows: $S_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 Vol_{i,t} + \beta_2 Vrt_{i,t} + \beta_3 Dummy_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$, where S_{it} represents the quoted spread, effective spread, realized spread and information asymmetry for stock i on day t ; $Vol_{i,t}$ is the daily traded shares (in thousands) of stock i on day t , after which the natural log is obtained; $Vrt_{i,t}$ is the daily volatility of stock i on day t , which is defined as the highest price – the lowest price for stock i for each day; $Dummy_{i,t}$ is a dummy

variable, with a value of +1 if publicly sponsored banking, otherwise its value is 0. The symbols *, ** and *** indicate significance at 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively.

	$Vol_{i,t}$ (1)	$Vrtn_{i,t}$ (2)	$Dummy_{i,t}$ (3)
QS	-1.19 (-32.50***)	2.37 (0.47)	0.43 (3.63***)
ES	-1.03 (-27.95***)	1.02 (0.20)	0.77 (6.46***)
RS	-1.06 (-24.97***)	9.78 (1.68*)	0.96 (7.00***)
IA	0.03 (1.86*)	-8.76 (-3.92***)	-0.19 (3.64***)

Comparison of price efficiency

Equations (5) and (6) are used to measure price efficiency. The results are shown in Table 7. As can be seen in panel A, the RRD_{t1} for publicly sponsored banking is 0.42, while for privately sponsored banking is 0.67. The gap of -0.25 is significant. The RRD_{t2} results (shown in panel B, Table 7) are similar to RRD_{t1} results. The findings indicate that price efficiency is better for publicly sponsored banking than privately sponsored banking. In other words, new information is less likely to lead to price error for publicly sponsored banking than private sponsored banking probably due to stricter governmental monitoring. Their better transparency leads to less price error for investors.

All in all, the H3 is rejected. The price efficiency is better for publicly sponsored banking than privately sponsored banking.

Table 7

Panel A

The regression model is formulated as follows $\gamma_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_i R_{mt} + \varepsilon_{it}$, where γ_{it} is the return of stock i on day t ; R_{mt} is the market return for day t ; α_i and β_i are the parameters that we want to estimate; ε_{it} is the error term. The pricing errors are calculated as follows:

$RRD_{t1} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \varepsilon_{it}^2$, where the n is the numbers of stocks. The symbols *, ** and *** indicate significance at 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively.

	Publicly sponsored banking (1)	Private sponsored banking (2)	Diff. (3)
RRD_{t1}	0.4204	0.6771	-0.2570*** (t=-8.56)

Panel B

The regression model is formulated as follows: $\gamma_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_{i1}R_{mt} + \beta_{i2}R_{mt-1} + \varepsilon_{it}$, where γ_{it} is the return for stock i on day t; R_{mt} and R_{mt-1} are the market returns for day t and t-1, respectively;

ε_{it} is error term. α_i , β_{i1} and β_{i2} are the parameters that we want to estimate. The pricing errors are calculated as follows:

$RRD_{t2} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{\varepsilon}_{it}^2$, where the n is the numbers of stocks. The symbols *, ** and *** indicate significance at 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively.

	Public sponsored banking (1)	Private sponsored banking (2)	Diff. (3)
RRD_{t2}	0.7170	1.5292	-0.8120*** (t=-2.08)

6. Conclusion

This study compares the market performance between publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking, including liquidity, payoff to investors and price efficiency. These three issues have important economic implication in finance, and are of deep concern to investors and policy makers. This study’s findings indicate that, first of all, privately sponsored banking have lower trading costs and better liquidity. Second, uninformed traders benefit by trading publicly sponsored banking stocks, while informed traders have the advantage

in trading privately sponsored banking. Third, price efficiency is better for publicly sponsored than privately sponsored banking.

In summary, there are pros and cons for publicly sponsored and privately sponsored banking. It is difficult to say which one is better. The recent flourishing expansion of privately sponsored banking encourages publicly sponsored banking to develop, while the increased

transparency and governmental oversight of publicly sponsored banking are textbook goals for privately sponsored banking. These are the directions for improvement of these two types of banking in the future.

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